

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 13: Change in the hierarchy of the EA class

Michał K. Tomczyk

Institute of Computing Science, Poznan University of Technology, Poznań, Poland

This document is part of a tutorial series on JECDM. URL: www.jecdm.cs.put.poznan.pl, email: jecdm@cs.put.poznan.pl.
The framework version used when preparing the document: 1.06.21.08.2025 (Java v. 17.0; IntelliJ IDEA 2023.3.8).

Abstract

This tutorial discusses a change in the hierarchy of the EA class.

Keywords: JECDM, EA, evolutionary algorithm, changes in the architecture

Contents

1 Introduction 1

1. Introduction

This brief tutorial document discusses a major change that took place in the hierarchy of the *ea.EA* class (*EvolutionaryComputation* module). So far, it has been a class highest in the hierarchy. It means that other frameworks' functionalities were built under the assumption that the instances of an evolutionary algorithm would be processed via the *EA* reference. For instance, when defining the experiment to be executed, the *TrialDataContainerFactory* was supposed to specify a way of instantiating the *EA*.

From this framework's version, however, *EA* was moved down in the hierarchy, and a dedicated *IEA* interface (*ea* package) delivering the core methods was introduced. Such a change is intended to introduce a greater degree of code generalization, which will help develop more creative evolutionary optimizers in the future.

More specifically, the current class hierarchy is as follows (all listed classes/interfaces are in the *ea* package):

1. *IEA*: The top-level interface. Relevant linked framework's components are altered to accept instances of *IEA*, not *EA*, as the primary input.
2. *AbstractEA*: Abstract, and very general, high-level class that implements *IEA*. It provides some common fields and functionalities.

3. *AbstractPhasesEA*: Abstract class that extends *AbstractEA*. It relies on the concept of dividing the processing into a series of functional blocks, called phases. It is the concept on which the *EA* class relies.

4. *EA*: The previously highest-level class. It now extends *ea.AbstractPhasesEA*.

On the compatibility with previous releases The change in the hierarchy required executing a minor update to other components that rely on the *EA* class for processing. These components include, for instance, performance indicators or a trial data container factory. In most cases, however, the changes boiled down to altering the relevant methods' signatures (*IEA* instead of *EA*), which did not raise many incompatibility issues. Nonetheless, one has to be aware of this change when switching to this framework's version, and may be forced to update their implementations accordingly.

Email address: michal.tomczyk@cs.put.poznan.pl (Michał K. Tomczyk)

URL: www.cs.put.poznan.pl/mtomczyk (Michał K. Tomczyk)